

Research Article

Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms in Gh, Ghr, GhSr and Insulin Candidate Genes in Chicken Breeds of Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

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The aim of this study is to evaluate genetic potential in chicken breeds raised in Vietnam. They include local chicken breeds (Noi and Tau Vang giving good health and meat quality traits but they are not intensively studied yet) and a commercial breed (Cobb 500 giving high growth performance and meat yield in industrial poultry production system in the world, including Vietnam). Therefore, candidate genes GH, GHR, GHSR and insulin related to these traits were investigated for identifying their single nucleotide polymorphisms by using PCR-RFLP method across different populations of chicken. The results provide basic foundation to continuously study the effects of genetic polymorphisms in the candidate genes on performance and meat quality traits of local Vietnamese chickens.

Keywords:

Genetic variation, Candidate genes, Chicken, Vietnam

INTRODUCTION

Most economic traits in farm animals show continuous variation and the fundamental genetic nature is very complex (Li *et al.*, 2010). The application of genetic selection methods in the poultry industry has resulted in increased growth rate and carcass quality (Zhou *et al.*, 2005). However, as a consequence, there has been incidence of health related problems such as obesity, sudden death syndrome, immunosuppression and leg problems (Kadlec *et al.*, 2011). Molecular markers related with one or more sets of traits may be helpful to concurrently improve production and health (Zhou *et al.*, 2005). The use of molecular marker-assisted selection has proven to be efficient and lead to the improvement in production performance in animals (Li *et al.*, 2008). Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), a type of DNA polymorphism which is bi-allelic but extensively distributed along the chicken genome has gained interest recently and the reason for this has been indicated by Beuzen *et al.* (2000).

The genes of somatotrophic axis play a crucial role in chicken growth and development (Nie *et al.*, 2005). The axis consists of essential components such as growth hormone (GH), insulin-like growth factors (IGF-I and II), their associated carrier proteins and receptors and other hormones such as insulin, leptin and thyroid hormones (Kadlec *et al.*, 2011; Nie *et al.*, 2005). Studies have shown that variation exists among these genes and this could function as candidates for the evaluation of their effects on chicken growth and development (Lei *et al.*, 2007). Results from previous researches have revealed that SNPs of the somatotrophic axis genes affect growth traits considerably (Nie *et al.*, 2005; Qui *et al.*, 2006; Lei *et al.*, 2005).

The purpose of this study was to identify SNPs in insulin, GH, growth hormone receptor (GHR) and growth hormone secretagogue receptor (GHSR) genes in local chicken breeds of Vietnam.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.1. Chicken Populations

This study used the three populations of chicken: Tau Vang with two different strains (CTU-LA01, n=84 and CTU-BT01, n=68), Noi (n=38) and Cobb 500 (n=32). The Tau Vang and Noi chicken represent Vietnamese local breeds with the characteristics of slow growth rate, low reproduction performance, high immune response and good meat quality traits, while the Cobb 500 with fast growth rate and improved feed conversion efficiency is a commercial breed commonly raised at industrial chicken farms in Vietnam nowadays.

2.2. DNA extraction

Genomic DNA samples were extracted from thigh/breast muscle tissues of all chickens from the three different populations using Phenol-chloroform extraction technique (Wickramaratne *et al.*, 2010) with minor modifications. Briefly, muscle samples from chicken were chopped into smaller pieces to aid in the digestion process. Then, 700 μ l of digestion buffer, 70 μ l of Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) 10% and 18 μ l of Proteinase K were pipetted into the 2ml Eppendorf tubes. In addition, 60-100mg of chopped muscle sample was added to the solution in the tube and the content was mixed on a vortex mixer and incubated overnight at 37°C. 700 μ l of phenol: chloroform (1:1v/v) was added the next day, mixed and centrifuged at 10.000 X g for 10 minute. Supernatant was recovered into a new clean tube. 700 μ l of Isopropanol and 70 μ l of Sodium Acetate (3M NaOAc) was added and centrifuged at 10.000 X g for 5 minutes. The supernatant was discarded after centrifugation and 1ml of 70% Ethanol was added to the tube to wash the DNA pellet. It was then centrifuged at 10.000 X g for 5 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and DNA pellet was air-dried, after which 500 μ l of TE 1x buffer (pH8.0) was added and mixed gently by hand to dissolve the DNA and incubated at 37°C for 12 – 24 hours and to be measured for the DNA concentration. A dilution of the stock DNA was done to the working concentration of 50ng/ μ l to be used for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) analysis.

2.3 Establishment of a PCR-RFLP assay

Polymerase chain reaction was performed in a total volume of 10 μ L, containing 1 μ L Buffer, 1 μ L MgCl₂, 0.20 μ L Taq polymerase, 0.25 μ L dNTP, 0.25 μ L of allele specific primer and 2 μ L of DNA. The PCR conditions were 94°C for 3 min to activate DNA polymerase, followed by 35 cycles of 94°C for 30s, annealing temperatures ranged between 58°C and 62°C for 30s, 72°C for 30s and a final extension of 72°C for 5min, and 4°C preservation. The PCR products were amplified by electrophoresis with 2% agarose gel at 110V, 400mA for 15min after which banding pattern was observed under UV light. Then, the products were digested overnight in an incubator at 37°C with 10 μ l of restriction enzyme. The digestion products were electrophoresed at 80 Volt for 30 min on 3% agarose gel. The PCR-RFLP (restricted fragment length polymorphism) fragment sizes were determined by visualizing the banding pattern under ultraviolet light.

This study was subjected to screen SNPs at loci G662A (intron 1, *Msp*I), T3094C (intron 4, *Msp*I) and C3199T (intron 4, *Msp*I) in GH gene (Nie *et al.*, 2005), G565A (*Eco*72I, intron 5) in GHR gene (Nie *et al.*, 2005), G656A (exon 1, *Msp*I) and C3678T (*Bsp*119I, exon 2) in GHSR gene (Nie *et al.*, 2005), and C1549T (intron 2, *Msp*I), T3737C (intron 2, *Msp*I), and A3971G (3' UTR,

MspI) in insulin gene (Nie *et al.*, 2005) in three different populations of chicken.

Table 1. Details of primers used for the SNP identification

Primer/locus	Sequence (5'-3')	GenBank	Length (bp)	Annealing temperature (°C)	Restriction enzyme
GH1	Fw: aacatcctcccaaccttc Re: ccctgcaaggttaggctca	AY461843	466	60	<i>MspI</i>
GH2,3	Fw: gcactgaggacgtggttat Re:ggcctctgagatcatggaac	AY461843	563	60	<i>MspI</i>
GHR	Fw: aacatctgcagagtcgggata Re: ccatggatcccagttgact	AJ506750	707	60	<i>Eco72I</i>
GHSR1	Fw: gtcgcctgcgtcctcctctt Re: acgggcaggaaaaagaagatg	AB095994	533	59	<i>MspI</i>
GHSR2	Fw: tgttgaaaaagagagaatgct Re: ccacacgtccttttatattc	AB095994	598	60	<i>Bsp119I</i>
Insulin1	Fw: tgttctgcattggcccatac Re: cagaatgcagctttttgtcc	AY438372	529	60	<i>MspI</i>
Insulin2	Fw: ctccatgtggcttcctctgta Re: ggcttctggctagttgcagt	AY438372	571	60	<i>MspI</i>
Insulin3	Fw: ggatctgaaaagcgggtctc Re: aatgctttgaagggtgcgatag	AY438372	281	60	<i>MspI</i>

2.4 Genotype analysis

Allelic and genotypic frequencies of the candidate genes in two local chicken breeds in Vietnam and a commercial breed were analyzed. The Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) was estimated using SNPStats (Solé *et al.*, 2006) (<http://bioinfo.iconcologia.net/index.php>).

RESULTS

Single nucleotide polymorphisms with various genotype and allele frequencies were identified at nucleotides C1549T, T3737C, and A3971G in the insulin gene, at nucleotides G662A, T3094C, and C3199T in the GH gene, at nucleotides G656A and C3678T in the GHSR gene as well as at nucleotide G565A in the GHR gene in the different populations of chicken (Table 2).

Figure 1: Digestion of restriction enzymes at loci of the candidate genes

At GH1, three genotypes AA, AG and GG were detected. The AA genotype frequency of the Cobb 500

breed was higher (0.56) compared to the other local breeds. However, the CTU-BT01 strain of the Tau breed

had the highest frequency for genotype AG (0.53). The highest frequency for GG was observed in the Noi breed (0.34).

At the loci GH2 and GH3, the genotypes CC, CT and TT were observed. The Noi breed did not show any genotype frequency for the CC genotype but showed a highest genotype frequency for the TT genotype relative to the breeds for the GH2 locus. However, all breeds showed more than 50% genotype frequency for the TT genotype. At the GH3 locus, high genotype frequencies for the homologous genotype TT was observed for all breeds with Cobb 500 showing 100% frequency but no frequency for the CC and CT genotype. At the GHR locus, genotypes AA, AG and GG were observed with genotype AA recording high genotype frequencies for all the breeds. The highest frequency (100%) was observed for the Noi breed but there were no genotype frequencies for AG and GG. The genotype frequencies for the AA genotype were higher in the local breeds than in the commercial breed.

At the GHSR locus, two groups GHSR1 and GHSR2 with genotypes AA, AG and GG; and CC, CT and TT were found, respectively. At the GHSR1 locus,

genotype AA showed approximately no genotype frequency and high genotype frequency was observed for all the breeds in relation to GG genotype. The Cobb 500 breed recorded the highest of 100%. No genotype frequency was observed for the TT genotype across the entire breed at GHSR2 locus. The genotype frequency of CC genotype was higher in the local breeds than that in the commercial Cobb 500 breed.

The insulin gene recorded similar genotypes CC, CT and TT at insulin 1 and 2 loci but AA, AG and GG at insulin 3 locus. At insulin 1 locus, the genotype CC recorded lower genotype frequencies in all breeds but there was no significant difference between the genotype frequencies of CT and TT. In the Insulin 2, there were also low frequencies for CC with the Cobb 500 breed recording no frequency for that genotype. A high frequency for TT was observed in all breeds. The Cobb breed showed the highest frequency (0.64) for the AG genotype while Noi breed showed the least frequency (0.33) at the insulin 3 locus. The genotype frequencies in the local breeds were higher for the AA and AG genotypes compared to the Cobb 500 breed.

Table 2. Allele and genotype frequencies within GH, GHSR and insulin genes in two local chicken breeds in Vietnam and a commercial breed

	Observed population					Expected population			HWE
	Genotype			Allele		Genotype			
GH1 (G662A)	AA	AG	GG	A	G	AA	AG	GG	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.44	0.45	0.11	0.66	0.43	0.44	0.45	0.11	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.53	0.39	0.08	0.72	0.28	0.52	0.40	0.08	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.32	0.53	0.15	0.59	0.41	0.35	0.48	0.17	NS
Noi breed (n=38)	0.24	0.42	0.34	0.45	0.55	0.20	0.49	0.31	NS
Cobb 500 (n=32)	0.56	0.31	0.13	0.72	0.28	0.52	0.40	0.08	NS
GH2 (T3094C)	CC	CT	TT	C	T	CC	CT	TT	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.05	0.33	0.62	0.22	0.78	0.05	0.34	0.61	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.04	0.29	0.68	0.18	0.82	0.04	0.31	0.66	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.07	0.38	0.54	0.26	0.74	0.07	0.39	0.54	NS
Noi breed (n=29)	0.00	0.14	0.86	0.07	0.93	0.00	0.13	0.87	NS
Cobb 500 (n=30)	0.13	0.33	0.53	0.30	0.70	0.09	0.42	0.49	NS
GH3 (C3199T)	CC	CT	TT	C	T	CC	CT	TT	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.05	0.22	0.74	0.15	0.85	0.02	0.26	0.71	*
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.06	0.17	0.77	0.14	0.86	0.02	0.24	0.73	**
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.03	0.28	0.69	0.17	0.83	0.03	0.28	0.69	NS
Noi breed (n=29)	0.07	0.14	0.79	0.14	0.86	0.02	0.24	0.74	*
Cobb 500 (n=30)	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	NS
GHR (G565A)	AA	AG	GG	A	G	AA	AG	GG	
Tau Vang Breed (n=148)	0.86	0.11	0.03	0.92	0.08	0.84	0.15	0.01	**
Line CTU-LA01 (n=80)	0.89	0.06	0.05	0.92	0.08	0.84	0.15	0.01	***
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.82	0.18	0.00	0.91	0.09	0.74	0.24	0.02	*
Noi breed (n=30)	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	NS
Cobb 500 (n=30)	0.10	0.17	0.73	0.18	0.82	0.03	0.30	0.67	*
GHSR1 (G656A)	AA	AG	GG	A	G	AA	AG	GG	
Tau Vang Breed (n=137)	0.01	0.13	0.87	0.07	0.93	0.00	0.13	0.87	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=73)	0.01	0.17	0.82	0.10	0.90	0.01	0.17	0.82	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=64)	0.00	0.07	0.93	0.04	0.96	0.00	0.07	0.93	NS
Noi breed (n=38)	0.00	0.18	0.82	0.09	0.91	0.00	0.09	0.90	NS
Cobb 500 (n=32)	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	NS
GHSR2 (C3678T)	CC	CT	TT	C	T	CC	CT	TT	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.82	0.18	0.00	0.91	0.09	0.83	0.16	0.01	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.87	0.13	0.00	0.93	0.07	0.87	0.12	0.00	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.76	0.24	0.00	0.88	0.12	0.78	0.21	0.01	NS
Noi breed (n=40)	0.88	0.13	0.00	0.94	0.06	0.88	0.12	0.00	NS
Cobb 500 (n=33)	0.58	0.36	0.00	0.76	0.24	0.57	0.37	0.06	***

Table: Continues

Insulin 1 (C1549T)	CC	CT	TT	C	T	CC	CT	TT	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.20	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.60	0.16	0.48	0.36	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.20	0.40	0.39	0.40	0.60	0.16	0.48	0.35	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.19	0.40	0.41	0.39	0.61	0.15	0.48	0.37	NS
Noi breed (n=38)	0.13	0.54	0.33	0.40	0.60	0.16	0.48	0.36	NS
Cobb 500 (n=32)	0.04	0.50	0.43	0.29	0.71	0.08	0.41	0.51	NS
Insulin 2 (T3737C)	CC	CT	TT	C	T	CC	CT	TT	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.03	0.28	0.69	0.17	0.83	0.03	0.28	0.69	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.01	0.23	0.76	0.13	0.88	0.02	0.22	0.77	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.04	0.35	0.60	0.22	0.78	0.05	0.34	0.61	NS
Noi breed (n=38)	0.03	0.20	0.78	0.13	0.88	0.02	0.22	0.77	NS
Cobb 500 (n=32)	0.00	0.48	0.52	0.24	0.76	0.06	0.37	0.57	NS
Insulin 3 (A3971G)	AA	AG	GG	A	G	AA	AG	GG	
Tau Vang Breed (n=152)	0.27	0.53	0.20	0.53	0.47	0.28	0.50	0.22	NS
Line CTU-LA01 (n=84)	0.27	0.54	0.19	0.54	0.46	0.29	0.50	0.21	NS
Line CTU-BT01 (n=68)	0.26	0.51	0.22	0.52	0.48	0.27	0.50	0.23	NS
Noi breed (n=36)	0.51	0.33	0.15	0.68	0.32	0.46	0.44	0.10	NS
Cobb 500 (n=27)	0.18	0.64	0.18	0.50	0.50	0.25	0.50	0.25	NS

NS means there is no significant difference between the observed and expected genotype frequencies under the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

DISCUSSION

Improving economic traits in chicken has increasingly become of interest and the identification and utilization of QTLs provide the potential for genetic improvement in selection programmes without slaughtering. Recent advances in molecular genetics have led to the discovery of genes, or markers associated with genes that affect meat quality (Gao *et al.*, 2007). Genetic diversity in local or domestic breeds of animals allows breeders and researchers to develop new characteristics in response to changes in environment, diseases or market conditions and maintain genetic diversity as well as improve productivity.

Recently DNA polymorphism in chickens and other types of animals in relation to different genes and their effects has been studied.

The chicken GH gene has numerous SNPs, some of which have been linked to body weight and skeletal growth in domestic fowls (Harvey, 2013), growth and carcass quality (Lei *et al.*, 2007; Nie *et al.*, 2005); egg production (Feng *et al.*, 1997) and disease resistance (Kuhnlein *et al.*, 1997). DNA polymorphisms in the GH gene have been studied in recent years in various animals and results have shown a close association with carcass characteristics. Lei *et al.*

(2007), observed a significant association with abdominal fat pad weight, abdominal fat pad ratio and crude fiber content of the breast muscle in SNP substitution from G to A in the chicken growth hormone (cGH) gene while Mehdi *et al.* (2012), observed a significant effect on body weight traits with SNP at G662A.

In the chicken GH gene, several SNPs in introns have been identified and reported to be associated with growth, egg production and disease resistance (Feng *et al.*, 1997, Qui *et al.*, 2006, Nie *et al.*, 2005a, Lei *et al.*, 2007). In this study, three SNPs (G662A, T3094C, and C3199T) were detected. Mehdi *et al.* (2012) observed that SNP at G662A had a significant effect on body weight traits.

In a study conducted by Qui *et al.* (2006), four SNPs were detected (A428G, C1594T, A3971G and T3737C) for the insulin gene. It was observed that both C1594T and A3971G were significantly associated with body weight while T3737C genotypes were significantly associated with small intestine length. In this study, however, only three SNPs (C1594T, A3971G and T3737C) were detected. Insulin plays an important role in cellular glucose uptake,

regulating carbohydrate, lipid and protein metabolism as well as promoting cell division and growth (Wilcox, 2005). In view of this insulin, it has been considered as a candidate gene in genetic analysis of complex traits such as growth rate, body composition and fat deposition (Qui *et al.*, 2006). In a study conducted by Qui *et al.* (2006), SNPs C1594T and A3971G were found to be significantly associated with body weight trait while T3737C genotypes were significantly associated with small intestine length. Lei *et al.* (2007), also observed an association of the insulin gene with muscle fibre density. In this study, however, three SNPs (C1594T, A3971G and T3737C) were detected.

The GHR gene was found in a research conducted by Lei *et al.* (2007) to be significantly associated with crude fat content of the breast muscle, abnormal fat pad weight and ratio. It was also observed that the GHSR gene was linked with fat traits and the INS gene was found to be linked with muscle fibre density. SNPs in the GHR gene have been studied in relation to growth rate and fat deposition (Geng *et al.*, 2008) and rate of growth in fast growing broiler strains and slow growing layer fowl (Zhao *et al.*, 2004); milk production and composition in Holsteins cattle (Aggrey *et al.*, 1999) and carcass weight and weight gain in beef cattle (Curi *et al.*, 2006). Polymorphisms in the chicken GHR gene have been found to be significantly associated with crude fat content of the breast muscle, abnormal fat pad weight and ratio (Lei *et al.*, 2007); egg production and body weight (Feng *et al.*, 1997).

Fang *et al.* (2010) detected a polymorphism in the GHSR gene in chicken, the dominant homologous genotype CC in the population was found to be associated with growth. In this result the CC genotype was dominant at the GHSR 2 locus and hence it can be associated with growth traits. The GHSR is involved in several physiological functions such as pituitary growth hormone secretion, food intake and energy expenditure (Shuto *et al.*, 2002). Polymorphisms in the GHSR gene have been found to be associated with growth traits in cattle (Zhang *et al.*, 2009); fat traits in chicken (Lei *et al.*, 2007); body weight and leg muscle weight traits in chicken (Fang *et al.*, 2010).

In conclusion, single nucleotide polymorphisms of the GH, GHR, GHSR and insulin genes existing in the various chicken breeds are containing great genetic potential resources for improving growth rate and meat quality traits because of their valuable characteristics on each breed group, in which Vietnamese local breeds such as Tau Vang and Noi developing in the backyard chicken systems are one of the good chicken production models ensuring animal welfare in Vietnam. These results indicated genetic contribution ability of the Vietnamese breeds to meat quality traits in the future as well.

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